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FACTORS OF STABILITY OF THE RUSSIAN FINANCIAL MARKET IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL SANCTIONS

2014-2024

The article presents a comprehensive analysis of the factors that ensured the stability of the Russian financial market in the context of unprecedented international sanctions in the period 2014-2024. Based on statistical data and analytical materials, the influence of macroeconomic, institutional, regulatory and technological factors on the stability of the Russian financial system is studied. The key transformations that occurred in the structure of gold and foreign exchange reserves, the banking sector, the payment infrastructure and the stock market, which contributed to the adaptation of the financial market to external restrictions, are identified. The effectiveness of the de-dollarization policy, the development of a sovereign financial infrastructure and operational measures of macroeconomic regulation is substantiated. Promising areas for further strengthening the financial stability of Russia in the context of ongoing sanctions pressure are identified. Technological innovations and digitalization of financial services have made a significant contribution to ensuring the stability of the Russian financial market. The active development of fintech solutions began long before the introduction of sanctions, but it was under the conditions of external restrictions that their role increased significantly. The remote identification and authentication system, the development of remote service channels and digital financial services ensured the continuity of financial services even in the context of sanctions restrictions and the disconnection of Russian banks from global payment systems. The development of a financial message transmission system based on distributed ledger technology increases the resilience of the financial infrastructure to external influences. Blockchain technology provides an additional level of protection and independence of the Russian financial system. The results of the study are important for the formation of a strategy for the development of the financial sector in the context of external restrictions.

Keywords: financial stability, economic sanctions, banking sector, financial infrastructure, stock market.

2014

2022

2014

2022

SWIFT,

2022

2,1 %.

2023

8,5 %,

2014-2024

1.

2.

(

3.
4.
5.

2022
643,2

()

300

2014

1.

I.

2014-

2024 ., % *

/	2014 .	2018 .	2022 .	2024 .	2024 / 2014, %
	41,5	22,7	10,9	32,9	-8,6
	46,1	31,7	21,7	15,32	-30,78
	0,1	14,2	17,1	4,7	+4,6
	9,5	18,6	21,5	32,1	+22,6
	9,4	6,0	5,8	4,7	-4,7
	1,9	4,5	3,9	5,82	+3,92
	1,5	2,3	19,1	4,46	+296

* [7]

1

41,5 % 2014 32,9 % 2024 .
(0,1 % 4,7 %) (9,5 % 32,1 %).

2022

2022

) 17 % , (120 %). (97 %

[1].

180

11,7 % , (). 2022 13,6

2014-2015 .
2022 (120)
(55-65) 2022
9,5 % 20 % 28 2022

(7,5 % 2023)

2014-2024 .

2.

2.

, 2014-2024 .*

	2014 .	2018 .	2022 .	2023 .	2024 .
(%)	0,7	2,8	-2,1	3,6	4,3
(%)	11,4	4,3	11,9	7,4	9,52
(, %)	17,0	7,75	7,5	16,0	21,0
USD/RUB ()	56,24	69,47	70,34	90,18	101,6
(%)	-0,4	2,6	-2,3	-2,5	-1,7
(%)	13,0	14,6	17,0	17,4	14,5
(.)	385,5	468,5	582,1	597,9	609,8
(%)	5,7	4,0	11,7	5,9	6,6

* [8]

2

2022 (-2,1 %)

2023 (+3,6 %),

2014 .

« » ,

« » Visa Mastercard 2022 .

1,76

2015 160

2024 .
6,3 % 2017

« »
77,8 % 2023

14 2024 .

() ,

SWIFT,

181

404 2018 549 2024 14
 2023 16,3 13
 2019 (),
 2024 249 2023
 40
 2013
 2013-2022 359
 333. 956
 [2]. 3.

3.

, 2014-2024 .*

	2014 .	2018 .	2022 .	2023 .	2024 .
	834	484	333	306	352
(.)	77,7	94,1	133,7	155,6	162,3
(%)	98,0	90,6	97,1	103,6	105,8
(.)	40,9	48,3	80,7	97,4	101,8
(.)	18,6	28,5	34,7	41,8	43,6
1.0 (%)	12,5	12,2	12,6	12,2	12,5
(%)	3,8	4,7	4,3	3,8	3,5
(ROA, %)	0,9	1,5	0,8	2,6	2,3
(ROE, %)	7,9	13,8	6,4	22,5	20,9
(%)	32,2	22,1	18,5	14,7	13,9
(%)	30,1	20,9	17,9	14,3	13,2

* [7]

3

I 2024 77,7 2014 162,3
 : 32,2 % 13,9 %
 — 30,1 % 13,2 %.

[3].

- 2022
 () ()

Clearstream. Euroclear

- 2022 80 %
 (50 %,)

182

2024 87 %

2023 76 %

2023

2023

2014 90,2 % 2023 3,1 %
85 % 2024

2024 25 CIPS, CIPS,

5.
5

52,2 % 2014 12,3 % 2023 — 42,6 % 14,8 %
— 17,6 % 36,8%. 7,5 % 27,4 %

5.

2014-2023 ., % *

/	2014 .	2018 .	2022 .	2023 .	2023 / 2014, %
,	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	—
	52,2	45,7	21,7	12,3	-39,9
	7,5	12,4	19,7	27,4	+19,9
	1,0	2,1	7,8	9,5	+8,5
	4,2	4,7	5,2	5,8	+1,6
	12,4	11,7	13,7	15,1	+2,7
	22,7	23,4	31,9	29,9	+7,2
,	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	—
	42,6	37,3	17,3	14,8	-27,8
	17,6	21,9	33,0	36,8	+19,2
	11,8	10,4	14,7	13,9	+2,1
	2,3	3,1	5,3	5,7	+3,4
	1,2	2,0	2,9	4,6	+3,4
	24,5	25,3	26,8	24,2	-0,3

*

[8]

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(2022-2023 .),

(2024-2030 .)

2022 ,

2022-2023 .

1. . . . // : , . — 2024. — 2(67). — . 45-66. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-2-45-66. — EDN IXFJJG.
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